

SCRAPPED COMPOSITE ICE-HOCKEY STICK SHAFTS FOR RESUSE IN CRASH ENERGY ABSORBERS

Patrik Fernberg¹, Thomas Bru², Roberts Joffe¹

¹ Dept of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden

² Dept of Polymers, Fibres and Composites, RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Sweden

RESTART

Re-use of ice-hockey sticks in energy dissipating structures

"... a pre-study with aim to evaluate possibility to reuse scrapped ice-hockey sticks for crash energy absorbing components ..."

In collaboration with :

GESTAMP
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Project aim

- Draft a road-map for a tentative ice-hockey stick reuse value chain
- Studies with respect to:
 - Identify research and development needs
 - **evaluate overall technical potential**
 - Make first assessment of potential market through inventories on
 - market size
 - value of re-use components
 - potential partners in value chain

Ice-hockey sticks

- Shaft-wall made from 15-30 layers of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy
- Fibres oriented with distinct orientation within each layer
- Different fibre-orientations in different layers
 - Most layers are with $+45^\circ$ and -45° -orientation
 - A few in with 0° and 90° -orientation
- Around 50-60% fibre (by volume)

The challenge

- Hockey-sticks are extremely lightweight and with tailored flexibility **but**:
 - with design that prioritize performance over margins against failure
 - often fails
 - hockey-players consumes large amounts of sticks
 - up towards 100 sticks/player/year in extreme case
 - expensive
 - 150-300 Euro/piece at retailers
 - difficult to recycle to constituents
 - epoxy thermoset
 - long continuous carbon fibres
- Energy recovery as only practically viable alternative currently

Photo: *PT/Gunnar Westergren, ** w www.thestickguru.com

Reuse potential

- Segments of sticks are intact after failure
- Intact segments may be reused
 - As construction elements from hollow straight carbon fibre structures with length ranging from 100 – 1900 mm
- Many ice-hockey players*:
 - 1 563 749 licensed players globally
 - 1 064 680 (Canada + USA)
 - 61 547 (Sweden)
 - 80 452 (Nordic countries excl. Sweden)
- Well known that composite tubes absorbs large amounts of energy during crushing
 - Efficient crash absorption elements
- **RESTART question: How can segments from scrapped hockey-stick shafts be reused for lightweight crash absorbing components e.g. in cars?**

Gestamp

WORKING FOR A SAFER AND LIGHTER CAR

Results - Mapping/inventory of 130 m scrapped shafts

From: LTU Project report, *Aitana Beato Irulegi*, Characterization of composites in sport application after service life

Results - Tensile modulus in direction along shaft

Objective to investigate

- variations within and between sticks
- variations between models

From:
LTU Project report, *Ethan Seguera Estevez*, Biobased/environmentally benign products for outdoor leisure/sport
LTU Project report, *Vanessa Hauschel*, Utilization of sport equipment after service life

Results - Quasi-static crushing of single shaft sections

- 50 kN servo-hydraulic testing machine
- Quasi-static compressive crushing (5 mm/min) between parallel steel plates

Results - Energy absorption of single shaft sections

Specific Energy Absorption (SEA)

- between 87 ± 4 kJ/kg to 112 ± 12 kJ/kg for five different stick models

Results - Crushing of single shafts vs virgin composites

Ref:
Feraboli 2007
Thornton 1979
& published data

Results - Preparation and testing of multi-shaft samples

- 7 samples each with 6 parallel shafts
- Mounted in ϕ 110 mm PVC cylindrical base by use of PU-foam
- Chamfered edges on shaft-ends to trigger progressive crushing
- Steel band over-wrapping to prevent splaying
- Compression crush tests in test machine 1000kN “Rörpressen” at RISE, Borås, Sweden
- Tests at constant displacement rate 10 mm/min

Results - Testing of multi-shaft samples

Crushing of sample 7

- Six valid test
- Generally a stable failure process
- Substantial variation in response
 - **Non-progressive crushing away from triggered edge for some elements after some time appears to be main cause for gradual load decrease with increasing crush distance**
 - Variation in segments performance

Work in progress

- Preparation of multi-shaft demo crash-boxes
- To be installed and mounted on actual car front-end test structure
- Impact testing at relevant conditions planned for June 2023.

Conclusions

- Scrapped shafts are high quality composite structures with reuse potential
- The mechanical performance of shaft wall material is high
 - although variation in properties exist between models and individual sticks
- Quasi-static tests on single shafts indicate that specific energy absorption capacity in crushing is very high
 - on par with the best composite structures available
- High quasi-static crushing performance is achieved for first generation multi-section samples
 - Larger tendency to have failure away from triggered edge than for individual segments
 - Sensitivity to triggering of progressive failure is hence higher with multi-section samples
- All results observed so far confirm the reuse potential of hockey-stick shafts in energy absorption applications

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Thank you for your attention!

